

Dynamic strain localization into a compaction band via a phase-field approach

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Compaction band
Dynamic strain localization
Grain crushing
Phase-field
Shear band

ABSTRACT

We present a new phase-field formulation for the formation and propagation of a compaction band in high-porosity rocks. Novel features of the proposed formulation include (a) the effects of inertia on the rate of development of compaction bands, and (b) degradation mechanisms in tension, compression, and shear appropriate for dynamic strain localization problems where disturbances propagate in time in a wave-like fashion to induce micro-cracking, grain crushing, and frictional grain rearrangement in the rock. We also present a robust numerical technique to handle the spatiotemporal formation and evolution of the compaction band. We validate the model by simulating a benchmark problem involving a V-shape notched cylindrical specimen of Bentheim sandstone tested in conventional triaxial compression. The model is shown to reproduce different geometric styles of deformation that include pure compaction, shear-enhanced compaction, and a combination of pure and shear-enhanced compaction, where the combination mechanism consists of a straight primary compaction band surrounded by secondary chevron bands.

1. Introduction

Localized deformation bands, including shear bands, dilation bands, compaction bands, and mixed-mode bands, are often observed in porous geologic media both in the laboratory and in the field (Fossen et al., 2018; Araujo et al., 2018). They typically occur in sandstones (Olsson and Holcomb, 2000; Baud et al., 2004), limestones (Baud et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2019), carbonates (Baud et al., 2009; Cilona et al., 2014; Shahin et al., 2022), and clay rocks (Ip et al., 2021; Ip and Borja, 2022a). Compaction bands are narrow zones of intense deformation characterized by little or no shear offset (see Fig. 1). Compaction bands are often oriented perpendicular to the direction of the maximum principal stress (Mollema and Antonellini, 1996; Fossen et al., 2011; Chemenda et al., 2012), but they can also be enhanced by shearing and develop obliquely with respect to the maximum principal stress (Eichhubl et al., 2010; Hill, 1989; Liu et al., 2015). Field observations and laboratory tests in porous rocks indicate that the occurrence of compaction bands is usually accompanied by significant permeability reduction, which plays a critical role in prospecting hydrocarbon reservoirs, CO₂ storage, and hazardous waste disposal (Olsson et al., 2002; Holcomb et al., 2007; Rutqvist, 2012; Stefanou and Sulem, 2014).

Over the last decades, compaction bands in high-porosity rocks have been the subject of extensive experimental studies (Vajdova and Wong, 2003; Tembe et al., 2006; Baud et al., 2004, 2009, 2017; Louis et al., 2006; Huang et al., 2019; Abdallah et al., 2021; Leuthold et al., 2021), field investigations (Mollema and Antonellini, 1996; Fossen et al., 2011, 2018; Chemenda et al., 2012; Cavailles and Rotevatn, 2018; Braathen et al., 2020), and theoretical and numerical analyses (Issen and Rudnicki, 2000; Aydin

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmps.2023.105228>

Received 20 October 2022; Received in revised form 17 January 2023; Accepted 23 January 2023

Available online 2 February 2023

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Fig. 1. Geological evidences of (a) shear-enhanced compaction bands (Fossen et al., 2011) and (b) pure compaction bands (Eichhubl et al., 2010) from *in-situ* field-scale observations. Abbreviations: SECB = shear-enhanced compaction band; PCB = pure compaction band.

et al., 2006; Borja and Aydin, 2004; Rudnicki, 2004; Sternlof et al., 2005; Stefanov et al., 2011; Prassa et al., 2022). Insights into the origin of this intriguing deformation style in rocks have improved significantly through laboratory testing and field observations. The incipience of a compaction band is well captured by most theoretical and numerical models, but its evolution beyond the initiation stage has continued to challenge the theoretical and computational modelers. Many conventional finite element models lack a characteristic length scale that inevitably results in spurious mesh dependence. Moreover, recent experimental observations suggest that the formation of compaction bands is characterized by two concurrent dissipation mechanisms, namely, plastic deformation and brittle/ductile fracture. In most models, only plastic dissipation is considered (Borja, 2004; Das et al., 2013, 2014; Marinelli and Buscarnera, 2019; Collins-Craft et al., 2020; Abdallah et al., 2020). Discrete element methods (DEM) have been used to model brittle/ductile fracture as it relates to the development of a compaction band (Marketos and Bolton, 2009; Chemenda, 2009; Sun et al., 2013; Duan et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2018, 2020b; Nguyen et al., 2022), but they are only appropriate for grain-scale simulations and have difficulty reproducing macroscopic deformation styles observed in the field. Meshless methods such as the smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) have also been employed to capture the kinematics of shear bands (del Castillo et al., 2021b,a), but not that of compaction bands.

Regularized energy-based numerical methods such as the gradient-enhanced method and the phase-field approach (Francfort and Marigo, 1998; Bourdin et al., 2000; Miehe et al., 2010a,b; Wu, 2017; Ip and Borja, 2022a) have offered appealing alternatives for simulating the failure processes in solid materials (Ambati et al., 2015a; Alessi et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2020a; Diehl et al., 2022; Sweidan et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2022). In particular, the phase-field approach possesses distinct advantages over other numerical techniques due to its standard variational form (Francfort and Marigo, 1998; Miehe et al., 2010a) that allows propagation of the discontinuity without requiring a special band tracing technique (Borja, 2000; Borja and Regueiro, 2001; Borja, 2008; Liu and Borja, 2008, 2010). In the phase-field approach, the discontinuous field such as a fracture or a deformation band is regularized by a more diffuse damage zone through a phase-field variable d and an internal length scale ℓ , where the latter can also serve to bridge the gap between the microscopic and macroscopic properties of the material. Moreover, in the phase-field approach the discontinuous field can be propagated without recourse to *ad hoc* criteria. Because of these advantages, the phase-field approach has now been used to address many discontinuous problems in solid mechanics, as well as to model the failure behavior of solid materials including concrete (Feng and Wu, 2018; Cheng et al., 2022), rocks (Bryant and Sun, 2018; Zhou and Zhuang, 2020; Fei and Choo, 2021; Liu et al., 2022), and composites (Zhang et al., 2020; Rao et al., 2022).

Early works on phase-field modeling have focused mainly on the simulation of brittle failure. In 2015, Ambati et al. (2015b) published one of the first articles to address ductile failure within the phase-field framework. They initially developed the framework at infinitesimal strains, but later extended it to finite strains (Ambati et al., 2016; Arriaga and Waisman, 2018) and combined the formulation with gradient plasticity-damage theory (Miehe et al., 2016). Borden et al. (2016) proposed a phase-field model to study the effects of plastic degradation function on ductile fracture. Meanwhile, several phase-field models with elastoplasticity were also proposed to simulate the brittle-to-ductile failure phenomena (Miehe et al., 2015; McAuliffe and Waisman, 2016; Chu et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2020a; Wu et al., 2022) and shear band formation (Arriaga and Waisman, 2017; Xu et al., 2020b; Zhang et al., 2021; Zeng et al., 2022). In these aforementioned works, only metallic materials were considered along with deviatoric plasticity (Borja, 2013).

More recent applications of the phase-field theory have focused on the capture of localized deformation in geologic materials. Choo and co-workers (Choo and Sun, 2018a,b; Fei and Choo, 2020, 2021) considered the phase-field evolution of discontinuous media with pressure-sensitive plasticity to capture a wide range of failure modes from brittle fracture to ductile flow. Wang et al. (2019) derived the driving force characterizing the phase-field evolution based on the Mohr–Coulomb criterion for pressure-sensitive materials. You et al. (2021) considered the plastic work to develop a modified phase-field damage model simulating the brittle-to-ductile failure transition. Hu et al. (2022) proposed a hybrid phase-field model based on an implicit material point method for brittle–ductile fracture transition in geomaterials. In addition, the phase-field approach has also been coupled with fluid flow in recent works (Suh and Sun, 2022; Yang et al., 2021). However, most of the above works have focused only on the fracture and shear band formation in geologic media, and none has addressed the problem of compaction bands.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagrams of deformation bands: (a) sharp topology of localization zones and (b) the relevant phase-field regularized deformation bands. Abbreviations: CB = pure compaction band; SECB = shear-enhanced compaction band.

Most recently, Ip and Borja (2022a) proposed a phase-field approach for compaction band formation and propagation in rocks employing breakage mechanics and critical state plasticity. Their approach involves the solution of an elliptic partial differential equation (PDE) in the context of quasi-static loading and rate-independent elastoplasticity. They introduced a degradation function for deformation in compaction and shear to represent pore collapse mechanisms in both the elastic and plastic responses. We pick up from their work and present an alternative phase-field approach incorporating dynamic effects for compaction band formation and propagation in high-porosity rocks.

Dynamic strain localization involves the solution of a hyperbolic PDE in which the disturbances propagate in time in a wave-like fashion. The stress points within the problem domain could experience both compression and extension as the disturbance propagates, even if the overall response of the rock is dominated by compressive deformation, making the dynamic solution distinct from a quasi-static solution. We thus introduce separate degradation functions in compression, extension, and shear to capture the various deformation mechanisms leading to the formation and propagation of a deformation band. We show that the proposed model is equally capable of simulating different patterns and geometric styles of localized deformation, including those not previously observed in quasi-static simulations of compaction bands.

The structure of presentation is as follows. Section 2 presents the proposed phase-field formulation. Section 3 develops the numerical solution strategy. Section 4 solves a benchmark example of compaction band formation in a sandstone, while Section 5 discusses several other numerical examples. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions derived from this work.

2. Phase-field formulation

This section presents the proposed phase-field theory for a deformation band in general and compaction band in particular. We first formulate the equations characterizing the geometry and evolution of the band. Then, we present a constitutive theory appropriate for characterizing the band formation and propagation.

2.1. Phase-field characterization of a deformation band

We consider an arbitrary solid body $B \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ in the reference configuration, where n denotes the spatial dimension. We assume that B contains an internal discontinuity Γ that is approximated by the phase field variable $d(\mathbf{x}, t) \in [0, 1]$. Fig. 2(a) and (b) depict such a prototype discontinuity Γ_ℓ in the form of a deformation band with a diffuse topology and having a thickness of 2ℓ .

In the phase-field approach (Miehe et al., 2010a,b; Xu et al., 2020b), the surface of discontinuity may include fractures (strong discontinuities) and deformation bands (weak discontinuities), and is represented by the expression

$$\Gamma_B = \int_\Gamma d\Gamma = \int_B \gamma(d, \nabla d) dV, \tag{1}$$

where $\gamma(d, \nabla d)$ denotes the discontinuous surface density function, whose distribution is given in terms of an internal characteristic length ℓ as

$$\gamma(d, \nabla d) = \frac{1}{2\ell} d^2 + \frac{\ell}{2} |\nabla d|^2. \tag{2}$$

Let $\Psi(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \boldsymbol{\alpha})$ be the total free energy function in B , where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is the infinitesimal strain tensor and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is the vector of strain-like plastic internal variables. In the presence of a deformation band, the regularized form of Ψ , denoted as Ψ_ℓ , may be developed by introducing the phase-field variable d and its gradient ∇d as follows (see Bourdin et al. (2000))

$$\Psi_\ell(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, d, \nabla d) = \Psi_o(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, d) + \Psi_i(d, \nabla d)$$

$$= \int_B \psi_o(\epsilon, \alpha, d) dV + \int_B \psi_i(d, \nabla d) dV, \tag{3}$$

where Ψ_o and Ψ_i are the total free energies “outside” and “inside” the band, respectively,

$$\psi_i(d, \nabla d) = \mathcal{G}_c \gamma(d, \nabla d), \tag{4}$$

and \mathcal{G}_c is the fracture energy release rate associated with plastic dissipation and band “toughness” (Grady, 1994; Rudnicki and Sternlof, 2005). The free energy $\Psi_i(d, \nabla d)$ represents the energy that is released as a result of the formation of the deformation band, while $\Psi_o(\epsilon, \alpha, d)$ is the energy associated with the deformation of the body as a whole.

Based on the assumption of elastic energy depending only on the elastic strains and the plastic energy depending only on the plastic strains (Lubliner, 1972; Collins and Houlsby, 1997; Ziegler, 2012), the free energy density ψ_o can be decomposed into the following form:

$$\psi_o(\epsilon, \alpha, d) = \psi_o^e(\epsilon^e, d) + \psi_o^p(\epsilon^p, \alpha, d), \tag{5}$$

where ψ_o^e and ψ_o^p denote the elastic and plastic parts of ψ_o , respectively. For isothermal process, the second law of thermodynamics can then be stated in the form of the Clausius–Planck inequality (Simo, 1998; Truesdell and Noll, 2004) as

$$\sigma : \dot{\epsilon} - \dot{\psi}_o^e \geq 0. \tag{6}$$

The dissipation function can then be written as

$$D^p = \dot{\psi}_o^p + \dot{\psi}_i \geq 0. \tag{7}$$

The first term on the right-hand side of (7) represents the plastic dissipation in the bulk volume whereas the second term represents the plastic dissipation due to the formation and propagation of the deformation band.

2.2. Driving force

In the phase-field formulation, the energetic forces of the constitutive model drive the evolution of the phase-field variable (Miehe et al., 2015; Ambati et al., 2015b; Wu, 2017; Wang et al., 2019). For quasi-brittle materials, the energy balance can be expressed by setting the rate of band deformation as a function of the power of the driving force (Miehe et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2019).

We first quantify the geometry and evolution of the deformation band as follows. Taking the time-derivative of (1) yields

$$\dot{\Gamma}_B(d) = \int_B \dot{\gamma} dV = \frac{1}{\ell} \int_B d\dot{d} dV + \ell \int_B \nabla d \cdot \nabla \dot{d} dV. \tag{8}$$

Noting that

$$\nabla d \cdot \nabla \dot{d} = \nabla \cdot (\nabla d \dot{d}) - (\nabla^2 d) \dot{d}, \tag{9}$$

we can insert this last equation into (8) and use the divergence theorem to obtain

$$\dot{\Gamma}_B(d) = \frac{1}{\ell} \int_B (d - \ell^2 \nabla^2 d) \dot{d} dV + \ell \int_{\partial B} (\nabla d \cdot \mathbf{n}) \dot{d} dA. \tag{10}$$

In the phase-field formulation, the boundary condition on the phase-field variable takes the form

$$\nabla d \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \text{ on } \partial B. \tag{11}$$

Thus, the evolution of the deformation band simplifies to

$$\dot{\Gamma}_B(d) = \frac{1}{\ell} \int_B (d - \ell^2 \nabla^2 d) \dot{d} dV. \tag{12}$$

We next assume that $\dot{\Gamma}_B$ is induced by some net driving force of the form given by (see Miehe et al. (2015))

$$\dot{\Gamma}_B = \frac{1}{\ell} \int_B [\mathcal{H}^{\text{eq}}(\epsilon, \epsilon^p, \alpha, d) - \mathcal{R}] \cdot \dot{d} dV \tag{13}$$

Here, $\mathcal{H}^{\text{eq}}(\epsilon, \epsilon^p, \alpha, d)$ denotes a driving force responsible for the localization of deformation, while \mathcal{R} is some viscous resistance of the form

$$\mathcal{R} = \zeta \dot{d}, \tag{14}$$

where ζ is a viscosity parameter. The strong form of the phase-field evolution for localized failure at any material point can then be written as

$$\zeta \dot{d} = \mathcal{H}^{\text{eq}}(\epsilon, \epsilon^p, \alpha, d) - (d - \ell^2 \nabla^2 d) \text{ in } B, \tag{15}$$

subject to the boundary condition given in (11).

Due to the irreversibility of the deformation process, we need to impose the following constraints on the theory:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} d(\mathbf{x}, t) &\in [0, 1] \\ \dot{d}(\mathbf{x}, t) &\geq 0 \\ \mathcal{H}^{\text{eq}}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, d) &\geq 0 \end{aligned} \right\}. \tag{16}$$

It is worth noting that in high-porosity rocks, the localized failure driving force \mathcal{H}^{eq} is related to both the elastic energetic and plastic deformation states, whereas the viscous resistance \mathcal{R} simply depends on the time derivative of the phase-field variable d .

2.3. Degradation functions

Because the solutions of hyperbolic equations are “wave-like”, degradation functions in both compressive and dilative types of deformation must be introduced to accommodate for damage in both modes even if the expected deformation is mostly compressive. In this work, we utilize the classic degradation functions for opening-mode fractures and enhance the description further by introducing another degradation function based on crushing potential for compressive types of deformation.

The classic degradation functions for opening-mode fractures are of the following form: For the elastic free energy, we assume small deformation and isothermal condition and decompose the total strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ additively into an elastic part $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ and a plastic part $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$. In rate form, we have

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^e + \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p. \tag{17}$$

We evaluate the von Mises equivalent plastic strain as

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eq}}^p := \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \int_0^t \sqrt{\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p} d\tau, \tag{18}$$

and define

$$r = \frac{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eq}}^p}{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eq,crit}}^p} \tag{19}$$

as the normalized cumulative plastic strain, which attains a value 1.0 when the von Mises strain reaches a threshold value $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eq,crit}}^p$. We incorporate r into the Helmholtz free energy as

$$\psi = \psi_o^e(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, r, d) + \psi_o^p(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, d) + \psi_i(d, \nabla d), \tag{20}$$

which leads to elastoplastic coupling on the elastic free energy.

We consider an elastic degradation function of the form

$$g_1(d, r) = (1 - d)^{2r^m}, \tag{21}$$

where $m \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ is an exponent that controls the ‘speed’ of localized failure mechanism (Ambati et al., 2015b). In this work, we take $m = 1$. We also consider the following decomposition of the elastic strain tensor into volumetric and deviatoric parts,

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{vol}}^e + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{dev}}^e, \tag{22}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{vol}}^e$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{dev}}^e$ are the volumetric and deviatoric parts, respectively. Taking the purely dilatational part ψ_{vol}^{e+} , purely compressive part ψ_{vol}^{e-} , and mixed tensile/compressive-shear deformation part ψ_{dev}^e into consideration, the stored elastic energy density is then written as (see Amor et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2022).

$$\psi_o^e(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, r, d) = \psi_{\text{vol}}^{e+}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, r, d) + \psi_{\text{dev}}^e(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, r, d) + \psi_{\text{vol}}^{e-}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, r, d), \tag{23}$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \psi_{\text{vol}}^{e+}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, r, d) &= g_1(d, r) \frac{K^e}{2} \text{tr}^+(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e)^2 \\ \psi_{\text{dev}}^e(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, r, d) &= g_1(d, r) \mu^e \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{dev}}^e : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{dev}}^e \\ \psi_{\text{vol}}^{e-}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, d, r) &= g_1(d, r) \theta \frac{K^e}{2} \text{tr}^-(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e)^2 + (1 - \theta) \frac{K^e}{2} \text{tr}^-(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e)^2 \end{aligned} \right\}, \tag{24}$$

K^e and μ^e are the elastic bulk and shear moduli of the intact material, $\text{tr}^+(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \max\{0, \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})\}$ and $\text{tr}^-(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \min\{0, \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})\}$ are adopted to prevent the interpenetration of failure surfaces in the compressive regions.

The parameter $\theta \in [0, 1]$ in (24) is the crushing potential introduced by Ip and Borja (2022a) to degrade the elastic bulk modulus in compression. This parameter works in such a way that as $d \rightarrow 1$, the degraded elastic bulk modulus approaches a nonzero value $(1 - \theta)K^e$. On the other hand, we note that the elastic bulk modulus in opening-mode fracture approaches zero as $d \rightarrow 1$. The Cauchy stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ can then be evaluated from the equation

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \frac{\partial \psi_o^e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e} = g_1(d, r) \frac{\partial \psi_o^e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e} + g_1(d, r) \theta \frac{\partial \psi_{\text{vol}}^{e-}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e} + (1 - \theta) \frac{\partial \psi_{\text{vol}}^{e-}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e}, \tag{25}$$

where

$$\psi_o^{e+} = \frac{K^e}{2} \text{tr}^+(\epsilon^e)^2 + \mu^e \epsilon_{\text{dev}}^e : \epsilon_{\text{dev}}^e. \tag{26}$$

We next turn to the plastic free energy. Employing the same decomposition of the plastic strain rate into volumetric and deviatoric parts,

$$\dot{\epsilon}^p = \dot{\epsilon}_{\text{vol}}^p + \dot{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}}^p, \tag{27}$$

we can write the plastic energy density ψ_o^p as

$$\psi_o^p = \psi_{\text{vol}}^p + g_2(d)\psi_{\text{dev}}^p, \tag{28}$$

where

$$\psi_{\text{vol}}^p = \int_0^t \sigma : \dot{\epsilon}_{\text{vol}}^p d\tau, \quad \psi_{\text{dev}}^p = \int_0^t \sigma : \dot{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}}^p d\tau. \tag{29}$$

Here, g_2 is another degradation function defined by Bourdin et al. (2000) of the form

$$g_2(d) = (1 - d)^2. \tag{30}$$

Note that whereas the degradation function $g_1(d, r)$ allows for the explicit dependence of the phase-field variable d on both the elastic and plastic strain energy densities, the degradation function $g_2(d)$ does not depend on the elastic strain and is a function solely of the phase-field variable d . Moreover, the two degradation functions account for energy dissipation by both brittle-like microcracking/grain crushing phenomena and plastic-driven failure/friction/grain arrangement during the deformation band processes, in agreement with the microscopic observations in the laboratory (Fortin et al., 2006; Abdallah et al., 2021).

Remark. Compared to the formulation by Ip and Borja (2022a), the degradation function g_2 employed in the present formulation is applied directly to the plastic work, whereas the degradation function used in the formulation of Ip and Borja is introduced into the evolution of the preconsolidation pressure to reflect the shift in the void-ratio versus logarithm of pressure curve due to pore collapse.

2.4. Evolution of the phase-field variable

We derive the evolution of the phase-field variable d from the regularized total potential energy given by the expression

$$\Pi_\ell = \Psi_\ell + Y + K - W, \tag{31}$$

where

$$\Psi_\ell = \int_B \psi dV = \int_B (\psi_o^e + \psi_o^p + \psi_i) dV \tag{32}$$

is the total free energy,

$$Y = \frac{G_c}{\ell} \int_B \mathcal{R} dV \tag{33}$$

is the work done by the viscous force \mathcal{R} in forming and propagating the band,

$$K = \int_B \frac{1}{2} \rho \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{v} dV \tag{34}$$

is the kinetic energy of the system, with ρ = mass density of the rock and \mathbf{v} = velocity vector, and

$$W = \int_B \rho \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{v} dV + \int_{\partial B} \mathbf{t} \cdot \mathbf{v} dA \tag{35}$$

is the external work done by the body force $\rho \mathbf{g}$ and surface traction \mathbf{t} .

Taking the stationary point of Π_ℓ with respect to \mathbf{v} , using the divergence theorem on the surface integral, and localizing yields the overall equilibrium condition

$$\frac{\partial \Pi_\ell}{\partial \mathbf{v}} = \mathbf{0} \implies \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \rho \mathbf{g} = \rho \mathbf{a}, \tag{36}$$

where \mathbf{a} is the material acceleration. Furthermore, taking the stationary point of Π_ℓ with respect to d and localizing gives the evolution condition for the phase-field variable

$$\frac{\partial \Pi_\ell}{\partial d} = 0 \implies G_c \ell \nabla^2 d - G_c \frac{d}{\ell} - \frac{\partial \psi_o}{\partial d} = \frac{G_d}{\ell} \zeta d, \tag{37}$$

where

$$\frac{\partial \psi_o}{\partial d} = -2(1 - d)^{2r-1} [r(\psi_{\text{vol}}^{e+} + \psi_{\text{dev}}^e + \theta \psi_{\text{vol}}^{e-})] - 2(1 - d)\psi_{\text{dev}}^p. \tag{38}$$

2.5. Plasticity model

Based on thermodynamics, the total stress tensor can be decomposed as

$$\sigma = \xi + \chi, \tag{39}$$

where ξ is the shift and χ denotes the dissipative stress tensors referring to Ziegler's orthogonality hypothesis (Collins, 2003; Ziegler, 2012; Jacquey and Regenauer-Lieb, 2021). In our phase-field model for localized deformation bands in geological media, the shift and dissipative stress tensors can be written as follows

$$\xi = g_2(d) \frac{\partial \psi_{\text{dev}}^p(\epsilon^p, \alpha)}{\partial \epsilon^p} + \frac{\partial \psi_{\text{vol}}^p(\epsilon^p, \alpha)}{\partial \epsilon^p}, \tag{40}$$

$$\chi = g_2(d) \frac{\partial \psi_{\text{dev}}^p(\epsilon^p, \alpha)}{\partial \alpha} + \frac{\partial \psi_{\text{vol}}^p(\epsilon^p, \alpha)}{\partial \alpha}. \tag{41}$$

For the dissipative stress space in elastoplasticity, the shift pressure $\hat{\rho}$ and dissipative pressure π can be calculated in the following forms to evaluate the plastic components of the deformation

$$\hat{\rho} = -\frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\xi), \quad \pi = -\frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\chi), \tag{42}$$

which results in the effective pressure and the deviatoric stress invariant as follows

$$P = \hat{\rho} + \pi, \tag{43a}$$

$$Q = J_2(\chi), \tag{43b}$$

where Q is the von Mises dissipative stress and the effective pressure P in compression is regarded as positive.

In this work, the local yield surface $\mathcal{F}(\pi, Q)$ in the dissipative stress space (π, Q) is adopted as Collins (2003)

$$\mathcal{F}(\pi, Q) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi^2}{A^2} + \frac{Q^2}{B^2}} - 1 \leq 0, \tag{44}$$

where A and B are coefficients defining the shape of the yield surface, which are given by the expressions (Collins, 2003)

$$A = (1 - \gamma)P + \frac{1}{2}\gamma P_c \tag{45a}$$

$$B = \mu \left[(1 - \alpha)P + \frac{1}{2}\alpha\gamma P_c \right], \tag{45b}$$

in which μ , γ and α are dimensionless material constants. Moreover, in classical elastoplasticity the shift pressure is rewritten as

$$\hat{\rho} = \frac{1}{2}\gamma P_c^0 \exp\left(\frac{\epsilon_{\text{vol}}^p}{\Lambda_c}\right) \tag{46}$$

where Λ_c is the plastic compressibility and P_c^0 denotes the initial preconsolidation pressure.

In the effective dissipative stress space with an elliptical yield function $\mathcal{F}(\pi, Q)$, the flow rules of the plastic strain invariants are stated as follows

$$\dot{\epsilon}^p = \lambda \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \pi} = \frac{\langle \mathcal{F} \rangle}{\eta} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial \pi} = \frac{\langle \mathcal{F} \rangle}{\eta(1 + \mathcal{F})} \frac{\pi}{A^2}, \tag{47a}$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}^Q = \lambda \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial Q} = \frac{\langle \mathcal{F} \rangle}{\eta} \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial Q} = \frac{\langle \mathcal{F} \rangle}{\eta(1 + \mathcal{F})} \frac{Q}{B^2}, \tag{47b}$$

where η is the plastic viscosity with the specific unit of Pa⁻¹s, and $\langle \bullet \rangle := (\bullet + |\bullet|)/2$ are the Macaulay brackets.

2.6. Localized failure driving forces

Recalling the phase-field evolution of localized failure bands in (15), the localized failure driving force $\mathcal{H}^{\text{eq}}(\epsilon, \epsilon^p, \alpha, d)$ is written as

$$\mathcal{H}^{\text{eq}}(\epsilon, \epsilon^p, \alpha, d) = \mathcal{H}^e(\epsilon^e, r, d) + \mathcal{H}^p(\epsilon^p, \alpha, d) \tag{48}$$

where $\mathcal{H}^e(\epsilon^e, r, d)$ and $\mathcal{H}^p(\epsilon^p, \alpha, d)$ are the localized failure driving forces due to microcracking and plastic dissipations, respectively, which are explicitly calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}^e(\epsilon^e, r, d) &= \mathcal{H}_{\text{vol}}^{e+}(\epsilon^e, r, d) + \mathcal{H}_{\text{dev}}^e(\epsilon^e, r, d) \\ &= \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \left\{ \sigma(\epsilon^e, d) : \epsilon_{\text{vol}}^{e+} + \sigma(\epsilon^e, d) : \epsilon_{\text{dev}}^e \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{49}$$

and

$$\mathcal{H}^p(\epsilon^p, \alpha, d) = \mathcal{H}_{\text{vol}}^{p+}(\epsilon^p, \alpha, d) + \mathcal{H}_{\text{dev}}^p(\epsilon^p, \alpha, d) = \int_0^t \sigma(\epsilon^e, d) : \left(\dot{\epsilon}_{\text{vol}}^{p+} + \dot{\epsilon}_{\text{dev}}^p \right) d\tau. \tag{50}$$

3. Finite element implementation

The standard finite element method is used in this work. The method is combined with a staggered time integration solver, including the explicit central difference scheme and the forward-difference strategy, to find the stable solution for the displacement and phase field variables, respectively. The selected time step is smaller than the critical time step prescribed by the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy condition (Borden et al., 2012; Sanz-Serna and Spijker, 1986). A novel stress update procedure is also proposed to simulate the localized failure phenomena.

3.1. Spatiotemporal-discrete scheme

We consider the following interpolations for the displacement and phase-field variables at any point \mathbf{x} in the element domain

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{I=1}^N \mathbf{N}_I^u(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{u}_I(t), \quad d(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{I=1}^N \mathbf{N}_I^d(\mathbf{x}) d_I(t), \tag{51}$$

where \mathbf{u}_I and d_I are nodal displacement and phase-field variables at the I th node, respectively; N is the total number of nodes in each element; and \mathbf{N}_I^u and $\mathbf{N}_I^d(\mathbf{x})$ are the standard first-order finite element shape functions for the displacement and phase-field.

Moreover, the strain vector in Voigt form and the gradient of the phase-field variable are calculated as

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{I=1}^N \mathbf{B}_I^u(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{u}_I(t), \quad \nabla d(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{I=1}^N \mathbf{B}_I^d(\mathbf{x}) d_I(t), \tag{52}$$

where \mathbf{B}_I^u and \mathbf{B}_I^d represent the derivative matrices of shape functions for the displacement fields \mathbf{u} and the phase-field d .

The spatiotemporal discrete equations for the dynamic equations of equilibrium and the phase-field evolution can be obtained from the standard Galerkin approximation.

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{u}) - \mathbf{F}_{\text{int}}(\mathbf{u}, d), \tag{53}$$

$$\mathbf{C} \dot{d} = \langle \mathbf{Y}(d, \nabla d, \mathcal{H}^{\text{eq}}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, d)) \rangle_+. \tag{54}$$

Explicit expressions for the matrices are as follows:

- Mass matrix:

$$\mathbf{M} = \bigwedge_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{B^e} \mathbf{N}_e^{uT} \rho \mathbf{N}_e^u \, dB^e, \tag{55}$$

where N_e is the number of elements in the computational domain and $\bigwedge_{e=1}^{N_e}$ is the assembly operator.

- Damping matrix:

$$\mathbf{C} = \bigwedge_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{B^e} \mathbf{N}_e^{dT} \eta \mathbf{N}_e^d \, dB^e. \tag{56}$$

- External force matrix:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}(\mathbf{u}) = \bigwedge_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{B^e} \mathbf{N}_e^{uT} \mathbf{b} \, dB^e + \bigwedge_{e=1}^{N_e^t} \int_{\Gamma_t^e} \mathbf{N}_e^{uT} \bar{\mathbf{t}} \, d\Gamma^e, \tag{57}$$

where N_e^t is the number of elements where prescribed tractions are applied, and Γ_t^e denotes the prescribed traction boundary in the e th element.

- Internal force matrix:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_{\text{int}}(\mathbf{u}, d) = & \bigwedge_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{B^e} \left[g_1(d, r) \mathbf{B}_e^{uT} \mathbb{C} (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{vol}}^{e+} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{dev}}^e) \right. \\ & \left. + g_1(d, r) \theta \mathbf{B}_e^{uT} \mathbb{C}_{\text{vol}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{vol}}^{e-} + (1 - \theta) \mathbf{B}_e^{uT} \mathbb{C}_{\text{vol}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{vol}}^{e-} \right] \, dB^e, \end{aligned} \tag{58}$$

where \mathbb{C} is the stress–strain matrix, which can be decomposed into volumetric and deviatoric parts, i.e., \mathbb{C}_{vol} and \mathbb{C}_{dev} .

- Coupled plastic-failure dissipation matrix:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y}(d, \nabla d, \mathcal{H}^{\text{eq}}) = & \bigwedge_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{B^e} \left[(1 - d) \frac{2}{G_c} \left[r (\mathcal{H}_{\text{vol}}^{e+} + \mathcal{H}_{\text{dev}}^e) + (\mathcal{H}_{\text{vol}}^{p+} + \mathcal{H}_{\text{dev}}^p) \right] \mathbf{N}_e^{dT} \right] \, dB^e \\ & - \bigwedge_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{B^e} \left[\mathbf{N}_e^{dT} d - \ell G_B \mathbf{B}_e^{dT} \nabla d \right] \, dB^e \end{aligned} \tag{59}$$

For the staggered solver, the displacement fields are computed using the explicit central-difference integration scheme, while the phase-field evolution is computed using the explicit forward-difference time-integration strategy.

3.2. Stress updated procedure

Within the time interval $[t_n, t_{n+1}]$, we assume that the known variables are $\epsilon_{\text{tot},n}$, ϵ_n^e , ϵ_n^p , d_n , r_n . We can then calculate the trial volumetric strain tensor $\epsilon_{\text{vol},n+1}^{\text{trial}}$ and the trial deviatoric strain tensor $\epsilon_{\text{dev},n+1}^{\text{trial}}$. The stress updated procedure can be summarized as follows.

The volumetric and deviatoric parts of the elastic trial total stress tensor $\sigma_{\text{tot},n+1}^{\text{trial}}$ can be first computed as follows

$$\sigma_{\text{vol},n+1}^{\text{trial}} = g_1(d_n, r_n) \theta \mathbb{C}_{\text{vol}} : (\epsilon_{\text{tot},n+1}^{\text{trial}} - \epsilon_n^p) + (1 - \theta) \mathbb{C}_{\text{vol}} : (\epsilon_{\text{tot},n+1}^{\text{trial}} - \epsilon_n^p) \tag{60a}$$

$$\sigma_{\text{dev},n+1}^{\text{trial}} = g_1(d_n, r_n) \mathbb{C}_{\text{dev}} : (\epsilon_{\text{tot},n+1}^{\text{trial}} - \epsilon_n^p) \tag{60b}$$

Then, the equivalent stress at $t = n + 1$ is computed as

$$Q_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} (\sigma_{\text{dev},n+1}^{\text{trial}} : \sigma_{\text{dev},n+1}^{\text{trial}})} \tag{61}$$

Next, the discrete trial yielding condition is given by

$$\mathcal{F}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}(\pi_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}, Q_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}) = \sqrt{\frac{(\pi_{n+1}^{\text{trial}})^2}{A_{n+1}^2} + \frac{(Q_{n+1}^{\text{trial}})^2}{B_{n+1}^2}} - 1 \leq 0 \tag{62}$$

where A_{n+1} and B_{n+1} are the yielding shape coefficients at $t = n + 1$, which are

$$A_{n+1} = (1 - \gamma) P_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma P_c \tag{63a}$$

$$B_{n+1} = \mu \left[(1 - \alpha) P_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha \gamma P_c \right] \tag{63b}$$

Then, considering the Kuhn–Tucker conditions,

$$\Delta \lambda \geq 0, \quad \mathcal{F}(\sigma_{\text{vol},n+1}^{\text{trial}}, \sigma_{\text{dev},n+1}^{\text{trial}}) \leq 0, \quad \Delta \lambda \mathcal{F}(\sigma_{\text{vol},n+1}^{\text{trial}}, \sigma_{\text{dev},n+1}^{\text{trial}}) = 0 \tag{64}$$

the classical elastic predictor and plastic corrector, i.e., the return-mapping algorithm, is adopted to solve the elastoplastic solutions.

If $\mathcal{F}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} \leq 0$, the trial total stress tensor $\sigma_{\text{tot},n+1}^{\text{trial}} = \sigma_{\text{vol},n+1}^{\text{trial}} + \sigma_{\text{dev},n+1}^{\text{trial}}$ is located in the elastic deformation regime, which indicates $\sigma_{\text{tot},n+1} = \sigma_{\text{tot},n+1}^{\text{trial}}$. On the other hand, if $\mathcal{F}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} \geq 0$, the trial total stress tensor is not admissible, and the return-mapping algorithm is needed as a plastic corrector step.

The computational schematic of the volumetric and deviatoric stress components in the return mapping algorithm is depicted in Fig. 3. Using the plastic flow rule of Eqs. (47a) and (47b), the volumetric and deviatoric plastic strain increments then read

$$\Delta \epsilon_{\text{vol}}^p = \frac{\langle \mathcal{F}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} \rangle}{\eta (1 + \mathcal{F}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}})} \frac{\pi_{n+1}}{A_{n+1}^2} \cdot \mathbf{N}_v, \tag{65}$$

$$\Delta \epsilon_{\text{dev}}^p = \frac{\langle \mathcal{F}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}} \rangle}{\eta (1 + \mathcal{F}_{n+1}^{\text{trial}})} \frac{Q_{n+1}}{B_{n+1}^2} \cdot \mathbf{N}_d, \tag{66}$$

where

$$\mathbf{N}_d = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} \frac{\sigma_{\text{dev},n+1}^{\text{trial}}}{\|Q_{n+1}^{\text{trial}}\|} \tag{67}$$

and the following updated stress states $\sigma_{\text{vol},n+1}$ and $\sigma_{\text{dev},n+1}$ read

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\text{vol},n+1} &= \sigma_{\text{vol},n+1}^{\text{trial}} - \Delta \sigma^P \mathbf{N}_v \\ &= \sigma_{\text{vol},n+1}^{\text{trial}} - g_1(d_n, r_{n+1}) \theta \mathbb{C}_{\text{vol}} : \Delta \epsilon_{\text{vol}}^p - (1 - \theta) \mathbb{C}_{\text{vol}} : \Delta \epsilon_{\text{vol}}^p \end{aligned} \tag{68}$$

$$\sigma_{\text{dev},n+1} = \sigma_{\text{dev},n+1}^{\text{trial}} - \Delta \sigma^Q \mathbf{N}_d = \sigma_{\text{dev},n+1}^{\text{trial}} - g_1(d_n, r_{n+1}) \mathbb{C}_{\text{dev}} : \Delta \epsilon_{\text{dev}}^p \tag{69}$$

where

$$r_{n+1} = r_n + \frac{\Delta \epsilon_{\text{eq},n+1}^p}{\epsilon_{\text{eq, crit}}^p} \tag{70}$$

in which

$$\Delta \epsilon_{\text{eq},n+1}^p = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \Delta \epsilon_{\text{dev}}^p : \Delta \epsilon_{\text{dev}}^p} \tag{71}$$

Fig. 3. Schematics of flow directions at different confining pressures (indicated by the red arrow) and the general return mapping geometric interpretation.

Fig. 4. Plane strain compression of notched Bentheim sandstone sample: (a) schematic diagram, (b) mesh discretization and (c) enlarged zone of V-shape notches.

4. Benchmark problems

To validate our model, we consider the notched Bentheim sandstone specimens tested in triaxial compression by Vajdova and Wong (2003) and Tembe et al. (2006). The laboratory specimens had a diameter of 18.4 mm and a height of 38.1 mm. For purposes of analysis, we simulated these tests in plane strain with the geometric configuration shown in Fig. 4(a) and the finite element mesh shown in Fig. 4(b). The V-shaped notches in the numerical model are 2 mm × 2 mm, as shown in Fig. 4(c), resulting in an inner width of $18.4 - 2 \times 2.0 = 14.4$ mm for the numerical model. A total of 8776 triangular elements were used in the finite element mesh with $h_{max} = 0.4$ mm.

Based on the literature (Tembe et al., 2006, 2008; Ip and Borja, 2022a), the following material parameters were used in the simulations: mass density $\rho = 2450$ kg/m³, Young’s modulus $E = 19.2$ GPa, Poisson’s ratio $\nu = 0.268$, critical fracture energy release rate $\mathcal{G}_c = 1.0$ J/m², viscosity coefficient $\zeta = 0.1$, plastic viscosity $\eta = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ Pa⁻¹ s, plastic compressibility $\Lambda_c = 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$, and crushing potential $\theta = 0.1$. Also based on the literature (Baud et al., 2006; Jacquey and Regenauer-Lieb, 2021; Ip and Borja, 2022a), the following parameters for the plasticity model were assumed: $P_c^0 = 420.0$ MPa, $\epsilon_{eq, crit}^p = 0.1$, $\mu = 1.5$, $\alpha = 0.5$ and $\gamma = 1.0$. The computational time step was $\Delta t = 1.0 \times 10^{-7}$ s and the length scale parameter was $\ell = 0.6$ mm.

The simulations consisted of first applying a confining pressure of 250 MPa followed by an axial load of 2 μ m/s, emulating the loading sequence in the experiments. The calculated vertical displacement u_2 and phase-field variable d are displayed in Fig. 5(a) and (b). We observe that the compaction band first initiates at the tip of the two V-shape notches and propagates horizontally towards the center. The result is a thin compaction band oriented perpendicular to the major compressive stress, as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 6 compares the stress–strain curve for the simulated Bentheim sandstone sample with the quasi-static simulation of Ip and Borja (2022a). Both simulations employed a plane strain assumption, so the comparison is meaningful. Six representative points

Fig. 5. Numerical results of compaction bands formation in the notched Bentheim sandstone sample: (a) vertical displacement field (unit: m), and (b) compaction band formation.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the simulated stress–strain response with the simulation result of Ip and Borja (2022a) for the Bentheim sandstone sample under a confining pressure of 250 MPa.

corresponding to the snapshots shown in Fig. 5 are labeled in the stress–strain curve shown in Fig. 6. Both simulations predicted an initially hardening response with comparable peak strengths. However, substantial softening is observed in the current simulation. Compared with the simulation of Ip and Borja, the current simulation predicts a more pronounced re-hardening response after the compaction band has formed, similar to that observed in the laboratory experiments (Tembe et al., 2006, 2008). Because the laboratory experiments were conducted in triaxial condition whereas the two simulations were conducted in plane strain condition, the experimental curve was not superimposed in Fig. 6.

Remark. Like the formulation by Ip and Borja (2022a), the onset of a compaction band in the present work is determined by the critical energy release rate \mathcal{C}_c and not by a softening behavior. There is no bifurcation analysis needed in either work, so it is possible to form a compaction band even in the hardening regime.

Fig. 7 plots the equivalent plastic strain ϵ_{eq}^p and volumetric plastic strain ϵ_{vol}^p at three representative simulation stages. Qualitatively, we observe that the volumetric plastic deformation dominates the compaction band formation, with the volumetric plastic strain being much more intense.

Fig. 8 plots the initial yield stress predicted by the phase-field simulation on the deviatoric stress versus mean normal stress plane against the experimental data reported by Vajdova and Wong (2003) and the results of a theoretical analysis conducted by Tembe et al. (2006) employing linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM). The initial yield stress predicted by the phase-field simulation lies within the region defined by the experimental and theoretical curves. In addition, the inset in Fig. 8 also indicates that the failure initiation pattern during compaction band formation agrees well with both macroscopic and microscopic observations (Vajdova and Wong, 2003; Tembe et al., 2006).

Fig. 7. Equivalent plastic strain ϵ_{eq}^p (top row) and volumetric plastic strain ϵ_{vol}^p (bottom row) during the formation of a compaction band.

Fig. 8. Initial yield stress for the notched Bentheim sandstone samples obtained from the phase-field simulation, laboratory tests (Vajdova and Wong, 2003; Tembe et al., 2006) and LFM theoretical analysis (Tembe et al., 2006).

A comparison of ultimate failure patterns obtained from the phase-field simulation, laboratory experiment (Tembe et al., 2006), and breakage mechanics modeling (Das et al., 2013) is depicted in Fig. 9. This result was obtained after conducting mesh convergence studies with $h_{max} = 0.2, 0.3, 0.4,$ and 0.6 mm, and with the same characteristic length scale of $\ell = 0.6$ mm, which produced nearly identical solutions. Both the breakage mechanics and phase-field simulation results compare well with the experimental observations. However, we shall show in subsequent simulations that the proposed phase-field model can capture not only the main compaction band straight form but also the shear-enhanced and secondary deformation bands that form away from the mid-section.

The grain crushing potential θ was introduced by Ip and Borja (2022a) to limit the degradation of the elastic stiffness due to grain crushing during the formation of a compaction band. To investigate its impact on the phase-field simulations, four V-shape notched Bentheim sandstone samples were subjected to plane strain compression under a confining pressure of $\sigma_3 = 300.0$ MPa. The resulting localization patterns and mechanical responses are plotted in Fig. 10(a) and (b), respectively. It can be observed that θ has

Fig. 9. Comparison of compaction bands in the notched Bentheim sandstone sample obtained from: (a) phase-field simulation, (b) experimental observation (Tembe et al., 2006), and (c) breakage mechanics modeling (Das et al., 2013).

Fig. 10. Effect of the grain crushing potential θ on: (a) compaction band patterns; and (b) mechanical responses.

only a slight effect on the ultimate compaction band formed (Fig. 10a) but has a more pronounced effect on the softening responses as the compaction bands propagate (Fig. 10b).

In all four simulations, we also note from Fig. 10(a) that although the main compaction bands are straight and thin, they are surrounded by secondary chevron bands delineated by the light-blue regions. A similar deformation feature has been reported in the literature using viscoplastic constitutive modeling of compaction creep tests in porous rocks (Shahin et al., 2019; Shahin and Buscarnera, 2020). This intriguing deformation style has not been reproduced in the quasi-static simulations of compaction band formation (Ip and Borja, 2022a). This could point to the role of dynamic effects on the ensuing style of deformation bands observed in the field. Other factors that could impact the geometric style of compaction bands include the boundary conditions (Shahin and Buscarnera, 2020), heterogeneous distribution of porosity (Baud et al., 2015), rock anisotropy (Shahin et al., 2022), fluid flow (Zhang and Borja, 2021; Zhao and Borja, 2020), partial saturation (Ip and Borja, 2022b, 2023), and chemical reaction (Borja et al., 2023).

5. Numerical simulations

We also conducted a series of hypothetical numerical simulations on Bentheim sandstone samples to further demonstrate the capability and performance of the phase-field model. All simulations were conducted under 2D plane strain condition on a rectangular sample having a width of 50 mm and a height of 100 mm, see Fig. 11. The sample was first subjected to a confining stress and then loaded in the vertical direction by prescribing a vertical displacement on the top boundary at the rate of 2.0×10^{-3} m/s while holding the bottom boundary fixed along the vertical direction, see Fig. 11(a). To trigger strain localization, we recognize that rock samples are inherently heterogeneous even at the smaller scale (Bennett et al., 2015; Semnani and Borja, 2017), so a weak element was introduced at the center of the sample by setting an initial value of $d = 0.05$ for the phase-field variable, see Fig. 11(b) and (c).

Referring to Jacquy and Regenauer-Lieb (Jacquy et al., 2021), we assumed the following values of material parameters in the numerical simulations: mass density $\rho = 2450$ kg/m³, Young's modulus $E = 22.3$ GPa, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.17$, critical fracture

Fig. 11. Problem domain and boundaries: (a) geometry and boundary conditions; (b) unstructured mesh and (c) structured mesh.

Fig. 12. Effect of mesh discretization on (a) localized failure patterns and (b) $Q \sim \epsilon_a$ curves of two Bentheim sandstone samples in 2D plane strain compression tests with $\sigma_3 = 60$ MPa.

energy release rate $G_c = 1.0 \text{ J/m}^2$, viscosity coefficient $\zeta = 0.1$, plastic viscosity $\eta = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Pa}^{-1} \text{ s}$, and plastic compressibility $A_c = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$. Initial values of the plastic variables are assumed as: $P_c^0 = 20 \text{ MPa}$, $\epsilon_{eq, crit}^p = 0.1$, $\mu = 1.2$, $\alpha = 0.65$ and $\gamma = 0.8$. In the present numerical simulations, the computational time step and the internal characteristic length were taken as $\Delta t = 1.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}$ and $\ell = 8 \text{ mm}$, respectively.

5.1. Mesh sensitivity and convergence studies

To demonstrate the robustness of our approach, we study mesh sensitivity and numerical convergence on dynamic strain localization. Two numerical samples with the irregular and regular FE meshes (see Fig. 11b and c) are simulated in 2D plane strain compression tests with $\sigma_3 = 60 \text{ MPa}$. The comparisons of localized failure patterns and mechanical responses are plotted in Fig. 12(a) and (b), respectively. Fig. 12 shows that the location, orientation, and thickness of compaction bands obtained from the two models are approximately the same. The mechanical responses of $Q \sim \epsilon_a$ curves in two numerical tests are also similar, which demonstrate the mesh independence and low mesh sensitivity of our model.

To study the numerical convergence of finite element solutions, we focus on two kinds of numerical samples: (i) samples with different h_{max} and a fixed ℓ , and (ii) samples with different ℓ 's and a fixed h_{max} . The confining pressures in 2D plane strain tests are kept as $\sigma_3 = 60 \text{ MPa}$. For the fixed $\ell = 8 \text{ mm}$, the localized deformation bands and mechanical responses of three numerical samples are plotted in Fig. 13(a) and (b), respectively. The location and orientation of pure compaction bands in three Bentheim sandstone samples are close to each other. The numerical predictions of mechanical responses, i.e., $Q \sim \epsilon_a$ curves, in three samples are also similar, while we observe from Fig. 13 that the thickness of pure compaction bands increases as the ratio of ℓ/h_{max} decreases.

For the fixed $h_{max} = 1 \text{ mm}$, the localized failure patterns and the relevant $Q \sim \epsilon_a$ curves in three numerical samples with various ℓ 's are compared in Fig. 14(a) and (b), respectively. When h_{max} is fixed at 1 mm, we observe that ℓ/h_{max} has slight effects on the

Fig. 13. Effect of l/h_{\max} on dynamic strain localization in the numerical tests with the fixed $l = 8$ mm: (a) localized failure patterns and (b) $Q \sim \epsilon_a$ curves.

Fig. 14. Effect of l/h_{\max} on dynamic strain localization in the numerical tests with a fixed $h_{\max} = 1$ mm: (a) localized failure patterns and (b) $Q \sim \epsilon_a$ curves.

predicted compaction bands. The above comparisons further demonstrate the numerical convergence and mesh independence of our new phase-field approach for modeling dynamic strain localization.

For the fixed $h_{\max} = 1$ mm, the localized failure patterns and the relevant $Q \sim \epsilon_a$ curves in three numerical samples with various l 's are compared in Fig. 14(a) and (b), respectively. When h_{\max} is fixed at 1 mm, we observe that l/h_{\max} has slight effects on the predicted compaction bands. The above comparisons further demonstrate the numerical convergence and mesh independence of our new phase-field approach for modeling dynamic strain localization.

5.2. Dynamic strain localization process

To further study the dynamic strain localization process, we look more closely into the spatiotemporal localization and mechanical responses of the Bentheim sandstone sample in plane strain compression simulated with $\sigma_3 = 60$ MPa. Fig. 15(a)–(d) show the spatiotemporal distributions of d , u_2 , ϵ_{eq}^p and ϵ_{vol}^p , respectively. During the formation of the localized deformation band, we consider eight representative snapshots in Fig. 15(a)–(d) and denote them in the $\sigma_1 \sim \epsilon_1$ curve shown in Fig. 16(a), and in the $\epsilon_{vol} \sim \epsilon_1$ curve shown in Fig. 16(b). From Fig. 15(a)–(d), we observe that the concentration of accumulative equivalent and volumetric plastic strains drive the initiation and propagation of compaction bands with a maximum value of $d = 0.01$. The evolution of compaction bands is represented by snapshots I ~ IV in Fig. 16(a) and (b). The enlarged zones in $\sigma_1 \sim \epsilon_1$ and $\epsilon_{vol} \sim \epsilon_1$ curves indicate that the slight strain-hardening phenomena occurs during the formation of compaction bands. When the deviatoric loads increase, the dynamic strain localization at macro-scale is initiated around the weak point, and propagates towards lateral boundaries normal to the axial direction. The formation of compaction bands is accompanied with the recognizable strain-hardening process in the $\sigma_1 \sim \epsilon_1$ and $\epsilon_{vol} \sim \epsilon_1$ curves, as shown in Fig. 16. Furthermore, when comparing the spatiotemporal distributions of ϵ_{eq}^p and ϵ_{vol}^p , we find that the volumetric plastic strain in compression dominates the dynamic strain localization process.

5.3. Effect of confining pressure

To investigate the effect of confining pressure on the dynamic strain localization and mechanical responses, we simulate six intact Bentheim sandstone samples in plane strain compression with different σ_3 . The confining pressure σ_3 is changed from 10 MPa to 60

Fig. 15. Dynamic strain localization process at $\sigma_3 = 60$ MPa: Snapshots of spatiotemporal distributions of (a) phase-field variable, (b) vertical displacement, (c) equivalent plastic strain, and (d) volumetric plastic strain.

Fig. 16. Mechanical responses of dynamic strain localization process at $\sigma_3 = 60$ MPa: (a) axial stress versus axial strain, and (b) volumetric strain versus axial strain.

MPa in increments of 10 MPa. Fig. 17 shows the resulting localized deformation band patterns, suggesting that the confining pressure plays a critical role in the dynamic strain localization. Based on the ratio $\epsilon_{eq}^p/\epsilon_{vol}^p$, dilation shear bands, shear-enhanced compaction bands, and pure compaction bands can be recognized. When σ_3 is increased from 10 MPa to 60 MPa, the localized deformation band pattern first changes from a dilation shear band with a high orientation angle (Fig. 17 a–b) to a shear-enhanced compaction band with a medium inclination angle (Fig. 17 c–d), to a pure compaction band with a low inclination angle (Fig. 17 e–f). The slightly curved shape of shear-enhanced compaction bands is caused by the combined compressive normal and shear stresses. These results

Fig. 17. Effect of σ_3 on the localized deformation band patterns in the plane strain compression tests.

Fig. 18. Effect of σ_3 on (a) $\sigma_1 \sim \epsilon_1$ and (b) $Q \sim \epsilon_1$ curves for Bentheim sandstone specimens in the plane-strain compression tests.

indicate that our model can capture the transition from dilatant to compactive strain localization, which agrees with results from breakage mechanics theory (Cil et al., 2020).

Fig. 18(a) shows the relevant macro-mechanical axial stress versus axial strain curves for these six simulations. Fig. 18(b) shows the deviatoric stress $Q = \sigma_1 - \sigma_3$ versus axial strain ϵ_a at different confining pressures. We observe from Fig. 18(a) that the peak axial stress increases as σ_3 increases, while Fig. 18(b) shows that the peak deviatoric stress decreases as σ_3 increases.

At low confining pressures (10 and 20 MPa), the samples attain a peak stress beyond which strain softening occurs with a significant stress drop during the dilation shear band formation. At medium confining pressures (30 and 40 MPa), shear-enhanced compaction bands initiate and propagate, accompanied by a slight stress drop at the post-failure stage. At high confining pressures (50 and 60 MPa), a pure compaction band forms with a monotonic strain-hardening response. Fig. 19 provide the graphic illustration of the localization patterns over the whole range of loading conditions simulated using our model. The initial yield stress points of samples at low σ_3 are located in the dilatant regime, while the initial yield stress points at high σ_3 reside in the compact regime.

Fig. 19. Graphic illustration of the relation between plane-strain compressive loading paths (i.e., gray dash lines) and initial yield surface (i.e., blue solid curve) during strain localization.

Fig. 20. Effect of σ_3 on $\epsilon_{vol} \sim \epsilon_a$ curves in the plane strain compression tests.

Overall, as the confining pressure increases the localized deformation band pattern transforms from a shear band type with significant strain softening, to shear-enhanced compaction band with moderate strain softening, to pure compaction band with pronounced strain hardening.

The predicted $\epsilon_{vol} \sim \epsilon_a$ curves are plotted in Fig. 20. When the deformation band changes from a shear-band type to a pure compaction band, the minimum value of volumetric strain decreases. At the onset of localized deformation, we observe that the volumetric strain first decreases significantly due to grain crushing. As ϵ_a increases and the band propagates, ϵ_{vol} decreases slightly due to pore collapse. At low confining pressures, the sample dilates at the post-failure stage (see Fig. 20) due to grain sliding and rearrangement. However, at high confining pressures the sample compacts, indicating that pore collapse and porosity reduction continue during the development of pure compaction bands. All of these observations agree with experimental observations (Tembe et al., 2006; Abdallah et al., 2021).

6. Closure

We have simulated the dynamic formation and propagation of compaction bands in high-porosity rocks using the phase-field approach. Main ingredients of the approach include separate degradation mechanisms in compression, dilation, and shear to accommodate for disturbances that propagate in a wave-like fashion; and a staggered numerical time-integration strategy employing the explicit central difference scheme for the displacement field and the forward-difference scheme for the phase-field variable. We have simulated the formation of a compaction band in a V-shape notched Bentheim sandstone sample in plane strain compression and obtained a complex geometric style consisting of a main pure compaction band and secondary double-chevron bands propagating away from the main compaction band. This style of deformation is distinct from the style obtained by Ip and Borja (2022a) from a similar simulation based on a quasi-static formulation, underscoring the effects of dynamic strain localization on the ensuing

geometric style of localized deformation. We have also investigated the effects of confining pressures, mesh discretization, mesh sizes and internal characteristic lengths on the numerically predicted deformation band. A plastic strain-based index is proposed to differentiate between shear bands, shear-enhanced compaction bands, and pure compaction bands. Work is underway to incorporate the effects of anisotropy and creep (Semnani et al., 2016; Zhao and Borja, 2022; Zhao et al., 2018; Borja et al., 2020; Liu and Borja, 2022) on the localization of deformation in rocks.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yunteng Wang: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Figures, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Ronaldo I. Borja:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Wei Wu:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to acknowledge the financial support from the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) for Lise Meitner Programme - MultiCBPR (Grant No. M 3340-N), Otto Pregl Foundation of Fundamental Geotechnical Research in Vienna, and EU Horizon 2020 RISE project - FRAMED (Grant No. 734485) and EU Horizon 2020 RISE project - HERCULES (Grant No. 778360). The second author acknowledges the support from the US National Science Foundation under Grant No. CMMI-1914780. Moreover, authors also would like to Ms. Sabrina C.Y. Ip for her helpful discussion and comments.

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